

**CREATING OPPORTUNITIES FOR CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES
IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES
СОЗДАНИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЕЙ ДЛЯ ДЕТЕЙ С ИНВАЛИДНОСТЬЮ
В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ
ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ
ТА'ЛИМ МУАССАЛАРИДА НОГИРОНЛИГИ БОР БОЛАЛАР УЧУН
РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИБ ИМКОНИАТЛАР
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ABSTRACT

This article examines strategies for providing parents of children in inclusive education with special opportunities. The study explores approaches such as providing parents with knowledge, psychological support, involvement in decision-making processes, and access to resources. Organizing workshops, training sessions, and online courses for parents enables them to understand their children's individual needs and actively participate in the educational process. Psychological counseling and group training help reduce parental stress, strengthen their emotional resilience, and support children's social adaptation. Involving parents as active members of multidisciplinary teams, particularly in developing individual learning plans and participating in decision-making, significantly contributes to children's academic success. Access to libraries, educational materials, and online resources allows parents to effectively support their children at home.

Keywords: inclusive education, parental involvement, special opportunities, pedagogical support, psychological support, multidisciplinary team.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются стратегии предоставления родителям детей в инклюзивном обучении специальных возможностей. Исследование включает такие подходы, как предоставление знаний, психологическая поддержка, участие в процессе принятия решений и доступ к ресурсам. Организация семинаров, тренингов и онлайн-курсов позволяет родителям понимать индивидуальные потребности своих детей и активно участвовать в образовательном процессе. Психологическое консультирование и групповое обучение помогают снизить стресс родителей, укрепить их эмоциональную устойчивость и поддержать социальную адаптацию детей. Привлечение родителей в качестве активных членов многопрофильных команд, включая разработку индивидуальных планов обучения и участие в принятии решений, значительно способствует академическим успехам детей. Доступ к библиотекам, учебным материалам и онлайн-ресурсам позволяет родителям эффективно поддерживать детей дома.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное образование, участие родителей, специальные возможности, педагогическая поддержка, психологическая поддержка, многопрофильная команда.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada inklyuziv ta'lim oluvchi bolalarning ota-onalariga maxsus imkoniyatlar yaratish strategiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda ota-onalarni bilim bilan ta'minlash, psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlash, qaror qabul qilish jarayonlariga jalb qilish, resurs va imkoniyatlarga erkin kirish imkonini yaratish kabi yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Ota-onalar uchun seminarlar, treninglar va onlayn kurslar tashkil etish ularni bolalarning individual ehtiyojlarini tushunishga va pedagogik jarayonda faol ishtirok etishga rag'batlantiradi. Shu bilan birga, psixologik maslahat va guruh treninglari ota-onalarning stress darajasini kamaytiradi, ularni emotsional jihatdan mustahkamlaydi hamda bolalarning ijtimoiy moslashuvini qo'llab-quvvatlashga yordam beradi. Multidissiplinar jamoalarning faol a'zosi sifatida ota-onalarni jalb qilish, masalan, individual rivojlanish rejalarini ishlab chiqish va qaror qabul qilish jarayonlarida ishtirok etish, bolalarning o'quvdagi muvaffaqiyatini oshirishga sezilarli hissa

qo'shadi. Shu bilan birga, kutubxona, o'quv materiallari va onlayn resurslarga erkin kirish imkoniyati ota-onalarga uy sharoitida bolalarni samarali qo'llab-quvvatlash imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: inklyuziv ta'lim, ota-ona hamkorligi, maxsus imkoniyatlar, pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlash, psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlash, multidissiplinar jamoa.

Introduction

In recent years, creating equal opportunities in education and ensuring the right of every child to education has become the focus of global attention. The international community, including the United Nations (UN), UNESCO and other international organizations, is promoting an inclusive model of education. The principle of inclusive education implies the full inclusion of children with disabilities in the general education system, and also aims to equalize their educational opportunities with healthy students. This principle not only ensures the social and academic development of children, but also prepares them for independent and socially active life in the future. Today, digital technologies have become one of the main tools that make the educational process effective for children with disabilities. Virtual and distance learning opportunities, interactive platforms, screen readers, audio books, mobile applications and artificial intelligence-based systems create a learning process tailored to the individual needs of children. In this way, each child will have the opportunity to learn at their own pace and at their own convenience.

Digital technologies not only make the learning process inclusive, but also create convenience for educators. For example, teachers will be able to organize interactive lessons, track students' progress, and adapt lesson materials based on their individual level of development. At the same time, virtual and augmented reality tools help to present complex concepts in a simple way, which helps children with disabilities better understand the subject. International and local experience shows that the introduction of inclusive education through digital technologies not only increases equality among children, but also promotes their social integration. Therefore, educational institutions, government agencies, and international organizations are paying special attention to the creation of digital resources and special curricula for children with disabilities, as well

as the training of teachers in modern technologies. This process serves to develop the individual capabilities of children and improve the quality of education.

Literature review on the topic

In recent years, a lot of scientific research has been conducted on inclusive education and the use of digital technologies for children with disabilities. UNESCO and UN reports emphasize the principle of inclusive education, including the full inclusion of children with special needs in the general education system and the need to equalize educational opportunities (UNESCO, 2023). Research shows that digital tools — interactive platforms, screen readers, mobile applications, and artificial intelligence-based systems — significantly simplify the learning process of children with disabilities and adapt it to their individual needs[2].

Local research also pays special attention to this issue. Yarashev and Asadova showed that digital pedagogical tools, virtual and augmented reality, and adaptive learning systems serve to develop the learning and social skills of children with disabilities. Nargiza Atabayeva also highlights effective ways to encourage children to learn at an individual level using assistive technologies and digital content [2]. The literature shows that digital technologies not only make inclusive education more effective, but also promote social integration among children. At the same time, government policies and international projects, in particular support from UNESCO, UNICEF and UNDP, expand the possibilities for the implementation of digital resources and teacher training[4]. These studies will create a scientific basis for further development of inclusive education and the introduction of innovative methods in the future.

Research Methodology

This article was prepared by analyzing scientifically based literature (literature review) and comparing existing practices. In the process of research, scientific articles published in Uzbekistan and international sources, state policy documents, and inclusive education projects implemented by the UN and UNESCO were studied. In particular, the latest scientific research, methodological guides and practical recommendations on the use of digital technologies for children with disabilities were analyzed. These sources served to identify the theoretical basis of inclusive education and the possibilities of improving the educational process using digital tools.

In addition, the article analyzed examples from the practice of various educational institutions in Uzbekistan. For example, the experience of using digital platforms, interactive programs and mobile applications in schools and higher education institutions was evaluated. Through this, the effectiveness of educational resources for children with disabilities, their adaptation to their individual needs and the degree of simplification of the learning process were studied [3].

A qualitative analysis and comparative approach was used as a research methodology. At the same time, existing international and local experiences, project results and practical cases were integrated to assess the effectiveness of inclusive education and digital technologies. This methodology provides the article with a scientific basis and practical value, and serves to develop recommendations for further improving digital educational resources for children with disabilities.

Analysis and results

The analyzed literature and practices show that the use of digital technologies for children with disabilities makes the educational process significantly more effective. Digital tools, including interactive platforms, mobile applications, virtual and augmented reality systems, allow for the adaptation of education and meeting the individual needs of students. For example, screen reading programs and subtitled video lessons increase the participation of students with disabilities, which simplifies and increases the efficiency of their learning process in a general education environment.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the “Ishonch 2030” project, implemented in partnership with UNICEF and the Ministry of Preschool and School Education, is introducing an inclusive digital school model in 50 pilot schools. This project aims to create an individual learning environment for each child, including students with disabilities, and ensure their equal access to education. In the implementation of this project, school leaders and teachers were provided with intensive training in digital and inclusive education, which ensured their readiness to effectively use electronic resources and inclusive methods in the educational process. Research shows that digital technologies not only expand the scope of inclusive education, but also create opportunities for individual adaptation of the learning process of students, the introduction of adaptive teaching systems, and improved teacher-student communication. For example, adaptive teaching systems repeat complex concepts in

visual and audio forms, which is effective for students with different learning styles. At the same time, virtual and augmented reality tools help explain complex topics in a simple and demonstrative way, which is important for students on the autism spectrum or who are prone to visual learning [7].

However, there are also problems associated with the introduction of technologies. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, it has been revealed that teachers have insufficient digital competence, school infrastructure is poor in some regions, and financial resources are limited to purchase special technologies. Therefore, for the effective implementation of digital technologies, it is necessary to improve the skills of educators, modernize education policies, and attract financial resources through international cooperation. For example, the SmartED project, in partnership with UNICEF, the UN and other international organizations, has been funded with \$19.2 million to promote inclusive and digital learning in schools [6]. At the same time, digital technologies not only increase the efficiency of learning, but also promote the social integration of students. Through inclusive education, children with disabilities actively communicate with classmates, participate in team work and gain self-confidence. This increases the inclusiveness and fairness of the education system.

Conclusions and recommendations

The effectiveness of using digital technologies for children with disabilities in educational institutions is increasingly increasing. Digital platforms and specially adapted resources not only expand opportunities for inclusive education, but also help to realize the individual potential of each child. Through digital educational tools, the educational process can be convenient, flexible and effective for students with visual, hearing or other disabilities. At the same time, the support provided by state policies and international organizations encourages the introduction of digital technologies for educational institutions.

Projects funded by organizations such as UNESCO, UNICEF and UNDP play an important role in expanding equal opportunities in education and implementing digital educational resources in an inclusive manner. This increases the access of children with disabilities to quality education and their full integration into social life.

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